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3 *“I Will If You Will”* in Climate Mitigation:

4 Conditional Cooperation in the Lab[☆]

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Abstract

This study explores how the ability to express conditionally cooperative strategies affects collective action in a public good game which captures some of the tradeoffs faced by the parties of international climate negotiations. We rely on a laboratory economic experiment to investigate the relationship between group size and cooperation under a standard baseline and a common commitment condition relying on conditional cooperation strategies. Results show that the common commitment architecture significantly enhances and stabilizes cooperation, even in larger groups, provided that the group marginal return is sufficiently high. These findings have critical implications for the design of international climate agreements and other public good provision systems.

Keywords: Conditional Cooperation · Laboratory Experiment · Group Size · Climate Change

1 Introduction

At the 1992 Rio de Janeiro Earth Summit, the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development convened stakeholders in light of the recognition of the pressing need to stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous consequences. More than thirty years later, emissions are yet to decline. On the contrary, global carbon dioxide emissions from energy combustion and industrial processes are up about 60% (International Energy Agency, 2023). Urgent international action is necessary to avoid dangerous climate change. The consequences of unmitigated, runaway climate change, would be severe, especially in vulnerable regions that are disproportionately located in the Global South (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2023, page 5). Yet, engaging in climate mitigation is a collective action problem with global public good features, which makes it difficult to solve.

To shed light on such fundamental collective action problems, here we modify the public good game to study how protocols that leverage conditional cooperation may affect the outcome of the ensuing agreement. MacKay et al. (2015) suggest that one of the reasons for the limited success of climate agreements in reigning in greenhouse gas emissions is essentially free-riding: nations take a back seat and wait for others to lead the way, leading to a negative cycle of unambitious efforts. Their hypothesis – which we study in this paper – is that a negotiation protocol and treaty structure based on conditional strategies will favor climate cooperation by aligning individual and collective interests. “[I]n a typical laboratory experiment, players contribute to the public good in the first round... but less is shown in subsequent rounds because parties observe others acting in their narrow self-interest, and nobody likes being taken advantage of. That is, the initial ambition, if any, tends to vanish, and behavior tends to move toward the selfish equilibrium (Ledyard, 1995). We will argue, from different perspectives, that to

55 promote cooperation and discipline free riders, a collective goal must be translated into a reciprocal, *common*
56 *commitment*: an agreement to abide by rules that specify ambitious behavior, provided others abide by the same
57 rules.” (Cramton et al., 2017, p.2, emphasis added)”.

58
59 The appeal of conditionally cooperative strategies stems both from behavioral and theoretical considerations. First
60 of all, it enables decision makers to express their motivations for reciprocity. It also provides a strategic
61 reassurance that as contributor you cannot be taken advantage of by free riders, which makes it an individually
62 better strategy than unconditional cooperation. At the time Cramton et al (2017) were writing, though, no
63 experiments on common commitment were available to support their claim¹.

64
65 In related previous work about the empirical performance of climate clubs to foster cooperation (Casari and
66 Tavoni, 2024), we introduced the possibility for decision makers to submit conditional strategies: their choice set
67 included unconditional actions as well as strategies that conditioned their contributions to the public good on
68 others’ actions. A third party would combine the strategy profile of the group of decision makers and implement
69 an outcome that is compatible with their submitted strategies. In Casari and Tavoni (2024), cooperation increased
70 under a Climate Club but its success had been considerably less than what initially conjectured. Furthermore, a
71 treatment with simple conditional strategies did not support the view that they were a definitive solution for
72 international climate cooperation. The current project squarely focuses on conditional strategies and sets up an
73 ambitious attempt to test their viability in promoting cooperation by studying them in a clean and simple setup.

74
75 One major research question is whether – in case conditional strategies are effective in boosting cooperation –
76 the success can be scaled up to large groups. International agreements generally involve dozens of countries and
77 a result obtained for a handful of agents might not scale up. We thus investigate group sizes beyond those
78 comprising four or five members, as usually studied in experiments (e.g. Carpenter, 2007, Thöni and Volk, 2018,
79 Gürdal et al., 2024, Oechssler et al., 2022). The starting treatment is a group size of two, which is effectively a
80 prisoner’s dilemma game. If conditional cooperation fails in that setting, that would seriously question its
81 viability. We then enlarged the group size to up to fifteen members. We argue that if groups of that size are able
82 to cooperate, that would constitute meaningful positive evidence for our research question.

83
84 Our aim is to study conditional cooperation but in a fundamentally different way with respect to Fischbacher,
85 Gächter and Fehr (2001) and the multiple replication studies that followed. Those experiments identified the
86 existence of a behavioral tendency in public good games of voluntarily contributing more if on average others

¹ Interestingly, recent literature now explores the effect of introducing commitment mechanisms to study well-known problems of coordination. For instance, Avoyan and Ramos (2023) show that commitment-enhanced communication can significantly reduce coordination failures in the minimum-effort game.

87 contributed more. This marked a solid contribution to the field. Their design relied on the strategy-method to
88 elicit contributions in a one-shot public good game under twenty-one scenarios with a given level of others'
89 contribution. Its purpose was to map participants' preferences. In contrast, our aim is to understand if and how
90 those conditionally cooperative preferences can, in practice, support more cooperative group outcomes. In our
91 study, participants select just one strategy, and this strategy will be combined with the strategies of other group
92 members, which could be conditional or unconditional. Interaction is repeated to allow convergence on a stable
93 outcome. If conditional cooperators are too few, or too demanding, group cooperation may still fail. We thus
94 provide experimental evidence on which conditions are conducive to cooperation, when groups size and returns
95 on investments to the public good are varied.

96
97 The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a review of the literature. Section 3 and 4 describe
98 the experimental design and procedures respectively. Section 5 brings forward predictions. Section 6 presents our
99 results, and Section 7 wraps up with discussions and conclusions.

101 **2 Related Literature**

102 Our work contributes to several strands of literature, which relates to conditional cooperation, group size in the
103 provision of public goods, and international agreement on climate change. At least since Fischbacher et al (2001),
104 scholars have documented the presence of a widespread behavioral trait of conditional cooperation. The
105 pioneering experiment of Fischbacher et al (2001) considers voluntary contribution in a public good game in
106 groups of four players, and elicits willingness to contribute under several scenarios through the strategy method.
107 They report that about 50% of the participants are conditional cooperators, in the sense of contributing
108 monotonically more when others contribute more on average. Theory predictions instead are unresponsive to the
109 contributions of others and imply free riding. Such theoretical benchmark describes approximately only 30% of
110 participants. The reminder of participants exhibit other patterns, such as hump-shaped behavior (14%), where
111 individuals cooperate conditionally up to a certain level before subsequently reducing their contributions.² More
112 than a dozen replications basically confirmed this finding. Thöni and Volk (2018) review 18 studies and document
113 that between 40% and 78% of participants can be classified as conditional cooperators, while Fallucchi et al.
114 (2017) examine 6 different studies and show that the percentage of conditional cooperators ranges from 37% to
115 74% (Li and Noussair 2024).

² In an extension, Fischbacher and Gächter (2010) elicited beliefs about the contribution of others, and found that 55% of participants were conditional cooperators where as free riders were 23%.

117 While the above studies successfully document the existence of conditional cooperators, they also show that a
118 participant's response to an additional unit of contribution by others is generally less than one additional unit of
119 contribution. This pattern of conditional cooperation would be insufficiently strong to sustain aggregate
120 cooperation. We directly study in the lab if that is actually the case, or if there exist ways to leveraging
121 conditionally cooperative preferences to ratchet up cooperation in public good games. Recently, and
122 independently from us, other scholars have tackled a similar question. Reischmann and Oechssler (2018) study a
123 mechanism where participants are able to express their conditional decision to contribute to a public good game
124 in groups of five members, by sending a direct message stating the minimum number of contributors necessary
125 to them to contribute. They report higher cooperation when participant can submit conditional decision than when
126 they cannot. They also contrast complete vs. incomplete information about the per-capita returns to the public
127 good, and introduce a refinement to the equilibrium set, by ruling out equilibria that are in a sense exploitable.
128 While in Reischmann and Oechssler (2018) the decision to contribute was binary, in another related study,
129 Oechssler et al. (2022), the action space is more granular. Participants now can express conditional decisions by
130 sending two messages "*I am willing to contribute x units to the public good if in total y units are contributed.*" A
131 third study, by Gürdal et al. (2024) instead considers a public good game with four players where a conditional
132 commitment is handled by a mediator. Participants can submit a message such as "*I agree to contribute k portion
133 of my endowment if all other members send this same message; otherwise, I will contribute x units*". The latter
134 two studies also report a higher level of aggregate cooperation when conditional strategies are available.

135
136 We specifically address the link between group size and the ratcheting effect of conditional cooperation. This
137 aspect is particularly relevant for international agreement about climate mitigation, where the number of parties
138 involved is elevated. The reviewed studies about the direct role of conditional strategies in raising aggregate
139 cooperation consider group sizes from three to five, which exhibit both a limited range, and a small group size.
140 We explore whether the results hold up for an expanded range of group sizes, in particular for a larger group size.
141 There exists an experimental literature on the effect of group size on cooperation. According to Olson (1964),
142 voluntary cooperation among large groups is basically impossible but this position was challenged early on by
143 Chamberlin (1974) on empirical grounds. He shows that the connection between aggregate cooperation level and
144 group size is less straightforward than what Olson suggests. More recently, in a review of public good experiments
145 about the link between group size and cooperation, Li and Noussair (2024) finds that in some studies aggregate
146 cooperation tends to be higher in larger groups,³ while in others the results are "ambiguous results or no systematic
147 relationship regarding the effect of group size on cooperation".⁴ One key parameters is the adoption of a constant

³ Isaac, Walker and Williams (1994) [$n=4,10,40,100$]; Carpenter (2007) [$n=5,10$]; Diederich, Goeschl and Waichman (2016) [$n=10,40,100$]; Pereda, Capraro and Sanchez (2019), [$n=5,10,15, 20, 25,35,40$]

⁴ Isaac and Walker (1988) [4,10]; Capraro and Barcelo (2015) [$n=3, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 80, 100$]; Feltovich and Grossman (2015) [$n=2, 3, 4, 5, 7 15$]; Nosenzo, Quercia and Sefton (2015) [$n=2,3,4,8$].

148 marginal per-capita (MPCR) return. In that case, by design, the marginal group return from the public good
149 becomes proportionally larger as group size increases. This design feature, although it does not change the
150 equilibrium set, is known to behaviorally help aggregate cooperation. The empirically challenge in public good
151 games is to study aggregate cooperation as group size changes, when we keep the marginal group return constant,
152 and marginal per capital return is adjusted. To sum up, previous research has shown that conditional cooperation
153 is a common behavioral trait among individuals, the precise relationship between group size and conditional
154 cooperation remains unclear. This question also relates to the issue of complementarity studied in Chen and Liang
155 (2024). They conduct a theoretically guided experiment to determine the optimal team size for providing public
156 goods when efforts are complementary. They report that under low complementarity, a group of size 10
157 cooperates more than a group of size 4, and that under high complementarity the conclusion is the opposite.

158
159 A main motivation for this study comes from the literature on Climate Change International Agreements. The
160 theoretical literature on climate cooperation clearly emphasizes the need to design stronger international
161 agreements to slow down climate change. For instance, insights into conditional cooperation are included in some
162 of the briefs presented in Stavins & Stowe (2016). The paper emphasized the need to enhance the Paris Agreement
163 (PA) by identifying “options for elaborating and implementing [it].” Victor (2016), in particular, argues that the
164 PA is flexible as it allows countries to endogenously decide their level of mitigation commitments, and this is
165 crucial for the agreement to thrive. And one implication of this flexibility is the need to understand crucially the
166 emergence of international cooperation. Then, the bottom-up cooperation approach through the formation of clubs
167 — which is fully compatible with the PA— is discussed. The role of conditional commitment becomes apparent
168 as an incentive for bolstering international cooperation through bottom-up clubs, the argument goes. Furthermore,
169 in the same document Harstad (2016) acknowledges that, despite major challenges related to the length of the
170 cycle period set for the global stocktake, an advantage the agreement features is to allow for conditional emission-
171 reduction offers. In this context, MacKay, Cramton, Ockenfels and Stoft 2015 advance the idea of aligning
172 individual interests through conditional actions implemented by the nations. Then in the design of international
173 agreements on climate change, a protocol based on conditional strategies might favor climate cooperation
174 (Cramton, MacKay, Ockenfels and Stoft 2017). Casari and Tavoni (2024) took on this idea of conditional
175 cooperation and climate clubs and studied it in the lab. They report a widespread use of conditional and club
176 strategies but only a mild improvement in cooperation. Also Heitzig et al (2023) follow suit by proposing the
177 implementation of a decentralized, bottom-up approach in line with the insights presented in Stavins & Stowe
178 (2016). It is called the Conditional Commitment Mechanism. The framework is based on conditional cooperation
179 and has the aim of improving the effectiveness of the Nationally Determined Contributions of the PA. The core
180 idea is reiterated — the countries’ commitment is grounded on the actions of others. Also, Schmidt, and Ockenfels
181 (2021) analyze experimentally the negotiation of a uniform common commitment among participants in groups

of four members. The commitments are expressed in terms of contributions to public good game. Their results indicate that a uniform common commitment bolsters cooperation to a greater extent than other ways of negotiating contributions such as individual and complex commitments. However, group size incidence on the effectiveness of negotiations is not considered.

3 Experimental Design

Participants face a public good game, where contributions are voluntary and costly. The interaction is repeated for 30 rounds within a fixed group of n decision-makers. Every round, each participant receives an endowment of $e=10$ points and has just two actions x_i available: either keeping all the endowment e to oneself ($x_i=0$) or contributing it in full to the public good ($x_i=1$). The earnings π_i for participant i come from equation (1).

$$\pi_i = e[1 - x_i] + \frac{\gamma}{n} \sum_i x_i e \quad (1)$$

Where $\sum_i x_i e$ is the total contribution to the public good, and $1 < \gamma < n$ is the group return from contributing. Then, $\frac{\gamma}{n}$ is the MPCR of a contribution. The experimental instructions are neutrally framed without references to climate change or nations. The experiment is articulated into ten treatments, as illustrated in Table 1.

Treatments differ along three dimensions: group size, strategy set, and group return. We study group sizes of $n = 2, 3, 6,$ and 15 . Moreover, for each group size, we consider two different strategy sets. In the *Baseline* treatments, the strategy set consists just of the two actions: unconditionally free-ride — putting the endowment in the individual account —, or unconditionally contribute —putting the whole endowment in the group account. In the *Common Commitment (CC)* treatments, the strategy set is richer and comprises a total of $n+1$ options. More precisely, the strategy set includes the two unconditional strategies of the Baseline treatments, and, in addition, $n-1$ conditional strategies, where the participant commits to contribute provided that a minimum number $k=1, \dots, n$ of group members will also contribute to the public good, and otherwise commits to defect⁵. For instance, in the case of $n=6$, each participant can select one out of seven options on her input screen. Each participant can condition her contribution on whether at least 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 other group members contribute.

The third treatment dimension is the marginal group return γ : for eight treatments $\gamma = 1.8$, while for two treatments $\gamma = 4.5$ (Table 1). In the first wave of sessions, we studied the ability to cooperate for a fixed aggregate benefit from the public good regardless of group size for two main reasons. First, to better represent the international

⁵ Our setup studies conditional cooperation in a less favorable design than what suggested by Cramton et al. (2017): “in the “common commitment” version, players condition their contributions on others’ pledges: a referee ensures that all contribute the amount of the lowest pledge.” (p.8).

climate change mitigation situation, where on a planetary level the benefits of mitigation policies remain the same regardless of the number of countries that exists. Second, to stress test the ability to support cooperation as the group size increases. Previous public good experiments with settings similar to our Baseline show that increasing the marginal group return favors cooperation. Hence, as we increase the group size n , the MPCR declines from 0.9 in $n=2$, to 0.6 for $n=3$, 0.3 for $n=6$, and 0.12 for $n=15$. In a second wave of sessions, we studied two additional treatments for $n=15$ featuring $\gamma=4.5$, so that the MPCR in that case is 0.3. The treatments most comparable to them are, on the one hand, those with $n=6$ as they have the same MPCR of 0.3 and, on the other hand, those with $n=15$ with $\gamma=1.8$ as they have the same group size and choice set. Exactly half of the treatments are Common commitment, and the other half are Baseline, in order to study cooperative behavior in a public good game with and without the availability of conditional strategies.

Table 1: Treatments

	Group size	2	3	6	15
<i>n</i> :					
Strategy set:					
Baseline		48 (2)	69 (3)	102 (5)	120 (4) for $\gamma=1.8$ 120 (4) for $\gamma=4.5$ (<i>15-high</i>)
Common commitment (conditional cooperation)		48 (2)	69 (3)	96(4)	150 (4) for $\gamma=1.8$ 120 (4) for $\gamma=4.5$ (<i>15-high</i>)

Notes: Entries display the number of participants (number of sessions in parenthesis). The return is always $\gamma=1.8$ for $n=2, 3, 6$. For $n=15$, we have both sessions with low $\gamma=1.8$ (“UC15-l”) and high $\gamma=4.5$ (“CC15-h”). We ran a total of 36 sessions. A first wave of sessions was ran in 2023: June (9, 20, 21, 22, 27, 28, 29, 30), July (13, 14), October (30, 31), and November (6, 10); a second wave in 2024 for CC15-h: October (3,10,11, 14, 15) and November (11,12,14,20, 21, 26).

Next, we provide key details about the design of the Common commitment treatments in reference to three aspects: feedback information given to participants, how strategies are matched to determine individual actions, and nudges. Let’s begin with the results shown to the participants after each round. In the Baseline treatment, each participant can observe the actions of everyone. A table shows for each group member the ID and the corresponding individual action; the individual earnings is shown just for the participant. The Result screen displays also the results of all previous rounds. More specifically, a table shows the participant’s action and earnings by round, as well as the total number of cooperative actions in the group. In the Common Commitment, the feedback for the current round is richer: an additional column of the table shows the submitted individual strategy of every group member (instructions are in Appendix A)⁶.

⁶ Participants’ order in the results table is their group ID for the $n=2,3,6$ treatments. Such order remains constant across rounds, as the ID is assigned randomly to participants at the beginning of the session. For $n=15$, instead, participants are ordered from the most to the least pro-cooperative strategy submitted in the round. Given the table length, the aim to facilitate the reading of the table. In all treatments, in the result table the participant’s line is highlighted in a bold character.

239 A second aspect of Common commitment to clarify is how individual actions are determined starting from the
240 strategies, because a conditional *strategy* profile for the group may be compatible with multiple *action* profiles.
241 For instance, if all are willing to contribute but conditional on everyone else contributing, then both mutual
242 cooperation and mutual defection are compatible outcomes. In these situations, the experimenter will always
243 implement the most cooperative group outcome compatible with the submitted strategy profile. The reason for
244 this choice is twofold. First, experimentally, we are interested in assessing the robustness of conditional
245 cooperation to larger group sizes than those commonly tested in the lab (typically at most five or six subjects).
246 While conditional cooperation has been found to have a positive effect on cooperation rate in such settings, its
247 effectiveness is likely to diminish in larger groups, for reasons having to do with increased complexity (e.g. due
248 to the multiplicity of equilibria, discussed below) and our choice to reduce the marginal per capita return from
249 contributing in larger groups. Given such choices, it seemed exceedingly unfavorable for the prospects of
250 cooperation to select the equally arbitrary alternative of implementing the least cooperative outcome. Indeed, such
251 a choice would have rendered the conditional cooperation mechanism rather ineffective, since frequent cases of
252 multiple outcomes compatible with a strategy profile would have resulted in defection. Second, our choice to
253 implement the most cooperative outcome is motivated by the aim to shed light on the potential effectiveness of
254 introducing conditional strategies in climate change negotiations. We thus think of the algorithm for selecting the
255 outcome from the strategy profile as the experimental counterpart to an institution such as the United Nations
256 Framework Convention on Climate Change, which is designed to foster cooperation.⁷

257 Next, nudges are the third aspect to be described for the Common Commitment treatments. The nudge consists
258 of an individually-customized message that appeared in the Result screen. Only a subset of group members
259 receives the message and only in selected rounds. Here is a message as an example: “*Missed opportunity! Had*
260 *you chosen [GROUP ACCOUNT ONLY IF AT LEAST ONE OTHER CONTRIBUTES] and your group members*
261 *had done so as well, your earnings in this round would have been higher by [2] points.*” The parts within bracket
262 could change. The message always recommends to the participant a more cooperative strategy than the one she
263 actually selected. More technically, the nudging message suggests a specific counterfactual strategy and does so
264 only in those situations when the participant is pivotal: when there exists a strategy that could have made both the
265 individual and the group better off because it triggered the cooperation of others. The following two conditions
266 must be simultaneously satisfied: (i) individually selecting another strategy would have increased her individual
267 earnings, when holding constant the strategies of the other group members; (ii) as a consequence of that unilateral
268 change, the number of cooperative actions in the group would have increased.⁸

⁷ For instance, under the Paris Agreement countries have been required to submit their national climate action plans every five years since 2020. Each successive plan is meant to reflect an increasingly higher degree of ambition compared to the previous version.

⁸ There may be more than one counterfactual strategy that satisfy conditions (i) and (ii). The message suggests the strategy that is closest to the participant’s original strategy.

270 4 Experimental Procedures

271 We recruited 942 participants through a web-based recruitment system (ORSEE) by sending invitation emails to
 272 students from the University of Bologna of various fields. The experiment comprised 36 sessions and each session
 273 had between 18 and 30 participants. Everyone joined only one session. Participants in a session were randomly
 274 partitioned into groups of size n and always remained in the same group (partner matching). Participants received
 275 a randomly assigned ID number to ensure anonymous interactions, and communication among participants was
 276 ruled out. No eye contact was possible among participants. Instructions were read aloud at the start of the sessions
 277 and left on the participants' desks (Appendix A) and then participants answered a comprehension quiz of five
 278 questions. For every correct answer they received 0.10 euros. The experiment was conducted at the Bologna
 279 Laboratory for Social Sciences via computers and programmed using z-Tree 5.1.11 (Fischbacher, 2007). A survey
 280 was administered at the end of the 30 rounds. Average earnings were slightly above 17€ per participant (1 point
 281 = €0.004 for $\gamma=1.8$ and €0.002 for $\gamma=4.5$). There was no show-up fee, but everyone had a guaranteed minimum
 282 earning of 5 euros. Overall, a session lasted on average 92 minutes from check-in to payments.

283 5 Predictions

284 In the baseline case of the commonly used strategy set featuring a dichotomous choice between unconditional
 285 defection and unconditional cooperation, the standard prediction under self-interested rationality ensues
 286 across all group sizes: contributing nothing to the public good is always the best response, independent of
 287 what others choose. Mutual defection is the unique Nash equilibrium of this game.

288 Now, before stating our predictions regarding the common comment treatment, we will describe the general game
 289 involved. Recall that we expand the player's strategy space to allow for conditional cooperation in a binary linear
 290 public goods game, and the decision to cooperate or defect is contingent on the number of cooperators. That is,
 291 one chooses the minimum number of co-players that are required to cooperate in order to do the same. As in the
 292 standard game, one can still pick unconditional strategies prescribing to always cooperate or always defect. More
 293 precisely, the conditional strategies are defined on the basis of the cardinality of the set of players in the game.
 294 The decision is thus of the kind: "I will cooperate if at least k other players besides me do so," where $0 \leq k \leq n$.

295

296 Formally, player i receives an initial endowment e and decides whether to invest it or not in the public good,
 297 depending on how many others contribute, as in (2). Let $x_i(k_i) \in \{0,1\}$ represent the binary decision of player i
 298 to contribute as a function of k_i :

299

$$300 \quad x_i(k_i) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if at least } k_i \text{ coplayers cooperate (C)} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise (D)} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

301

302 where $x_i(0) = 1$ and $x_i(n) = 0$ capture unconditional cooperation and unconditional defection, respectively. k_i
303 can be interpreted as individual i 's cooperation threshold. Players have a total of $(n + 1)$ available strategies,
304 corresponding to the individual strategy set $S_i = \{x_i(0), x_i(1), x_i(2), \dots, x_i(n)\}$. A strategy profile $x =$
305 $(x_1(k_1), x_2(k_2), \dots, x_n(k_n)) \in S$ is given by the decision vectors of all players. The combination of individual
306 strategies within a strategy profile determines whether each player will cooperate or defect (0 or 1). Then, we
307 simply take the payoff function (1) in terms of (2).

308

309 *Example 1*

310 Suppose $n = 6$ with the following strategy profile: $(x_1(0), x_2(1), x_3(2), x_4(3), x_5(6), x_6(6))$. This profile leads
311 to an outcome in which the first four players contribute to the public good, whereas the last two do not:
312 (C, C, C, C, D, D) . Consider instead the strategy profile $(x_1(1), x_2(1), x_3(3), x_4(3), x_5(6), x_6(6))$. Notice that
313 several outcomes are compatible with the combinations of strategies in this profile. See Table 2. However, we
314 have already advanced that when multiple outcomes are compatible with a given strategy profile, we will
315 implement the most cooperative for the reasons stated above. Hence, the implemented outcome will be the one
316 where four players cooperate and two defect.

317

Table 2

Strategy Profile	Outcomes
	(D,D,D,D,D,D)
$(x_1(1), x_2(1), x_3(3), x_4(3), x_5(6), x_6(6),)$	(C,C,C,C,D,D)
	(C,C,D,D,D,D)

318

319 Next, in this treatment, depending on n and γ , we observe outcomes of partial and full cooperation, as well as full
320 defection, all supported through Nash equilibria. Moreover, the numerosity of equilibria is determined by the
321 value of γ , according to some properties related to the combination of conditional strategies in a strategy profile.
322 An overview of such properties is provided in Appendix D, where we present an approach that enables us to
323 pinpoint equilibrium strategy profiles and discard those profiles that result in analogous outcomes, yet do not
324 constitute equilibria. We now show the predictions by group size below.

325 *Group size $n=2$*

Here each player here has the following set of strategies $\{x(0), x(1), x(2)\}$, where $x(1)$ stands for *cooperate if the other does so* ($k=1$). The general game will look like the one below. Player 1 chooses rows and Player 2 chooses columns. It is easy to see that this game (Table 3) exhibits two Nash equilibria: $(x(1), x(1))^* \rightarrow (C,C)$ and $(x(2), x(2))^* \rightarrow (D,D)$.

Table 3. Example of the game with conditional strategies and $n=2$

	$x(0) \rightarrow C$	$x(1) \rightarrow C$	$x(2) \rightarrow D$
$x(0) \rightarrow C$	$\gamma e, \gamma e$	$\gamma e, \gamma e$	$\frac{\gamma e}{2}, e + \frac{\gamma e}{2}$
$x(1) \rightarrow C$	$\gamma e, \gamma e$	$\gamma e, \gamma e$	e, e
$x(2) \rightarrow D$	$e + \frac{\gamma e}{2}, \frac{\gamma e}{2}$	e, e	e, e

In the context of group sizes greater than two, the number equilibrium strategy profiles exhibit sensitivity to the value γ . Therefore, the predictions for groups of sizes 3, 6, and 15 are contingent on the actual parameter values employed in the experiment ($\gamma=1.8$ and $\gamma'=4.5$). In the study, group size 3 and 6 are analyzed under γ , while the case $n=15$ is examined in two scenarios defined by the values of γ and γ' . Let us have a look.

Group size $n=3$

Here the game has 14 equilibrium profiles, whose outcomes range from full defection to partial and full cooperation. Table 4 below lists the Nash equilibria of this game. To simplify notation, the numbers in parenthesis indicate the strategy (k_i) player i is following (from left to right p_1, p_2, p_3). *Perm* means that the permutations of the profile entries are also equilibria given the symmetry of the game.

Table 4 Nash Equilibria (NE), Outcomes and Cardinality for $n=3$

n	NE	Outcomes	Cardinality
3	NE: = {Perm(2,2,0) * Per(2,2,1)*, (2,2,2)*, Per(1,3,1)*, Per(2,3,3)*, (3,3,3)* }	O: = {(C,C,C), (C,D,C), (D,D,D)}	NE =14 and O =3

Next, as the group size increases, so does the number of Nash equilibria of the associated game. Then, in contrast to the cases $n=2$ and $n=3$, we found a plethora of Nash equilibria for group sizes $n=6$ and $n=15$, so much so that it might not be enlightening to show an extensive list here. However, we describe below the effective outcomes supported through the Nash equilibria.

Group size $n=6$

353 There are four outcome cases supported through equilibrium strategies. In addition to full defection and full
354 cooperation, there are two levels of partial cooperation. One is where four players end up cooperating and two
355 players defect, and the second is where only one player defects.

356 *Group size $n=15$, $\gamma=1.8$ and $\gamma=4.5$*

357 For $n=15$ with $\gamma=4.5$, there are 13 possible equilibrium outcomes, whereas for $n=15$ with $\gamma=1.8$, there are 8
358 possible equilibrium outcomes. Full cooperation and full defection can be supported through strategy equilibrium
359 profiles. As for the partial cooperation equilibrium outcomes, under $n=15$ with $\gamma=1.8$, there are 6 cases
360 corresponding to cooperative outcome sizes ranging from 9 to 14. In contrast, under $n=15$ with $\gamma=4.5$, 11 partial
361 cooperation outcomes are sustained through equilibrium profiles, with sizes spanning from 4 to 14.

362 **6 Results**

363 This section presents empirical findings, which are organized into five results that highlight the role of conditional
364 strategies and group size, in particular their impact on cooperation levels. For the Baseline treatments, the results
365 are squarely in line with the previous literature on public good experiments. More specifically, within a group,
366 cooperation levels decline over time. Moreover, for higher marginal group returns (1.8 vs. 4.5), cooperation levels
367 increase (from 23% to 40%, $n=15$). Finally, the larger the group the lower are the cooperation levels when we
368 keep constant the marginal group return (from 83% for $n=2$ to 23% for $n=15$).

369 **Result 1. Common Commitment.** *The ability to submit conditional strategies substantially increases*
370 *cooperation for all group sizes, provided that the group marginal return is sufficiently high.*

371 Support for Result 1 is in Figure 1. Common commitment boosted cooperation levels between 4 and 25 percentage
372 points in comparison to Baseline. These treatment differences – 15 percentage points for $n=2$, 21 for $n=3$, 25 for
373 $n=6$, 4 for $n=15$, and 24 for $n=15$ -high – were statistically significant according to a Mann-Whitney test for all
374 group sizes, except for $n=15$. Result 1 is reflected also in the treatment differences in terms of individual earnings,
375 which exhibit the same comparative static across treatments as cooperation rates.⁹

⁹ Wilcoxon test of Baseline vs. Common commitment based on average individual earnings over 30 rounds, no. obs.=48 vs. 48, 69 vs. 69, 102 vs. 96, 120 vs. 150, 120 vs. 120, respectively.

Figure 1. Aggregate cooperation rates by group size.

378

379 Notes: Statistical significance: *** = 0.01, ** = 0.05, * = 0.10 of a Mann-Whitney test of Baseline vs. Common commitment
 380 cooperation rate. The unit of observation is the average number of cooperators in a group over 30 rounds, no. obs. =24 vs. 24, 23 vs.
 381 23, 17 vs. 16, 8 vs.10, 8 vs. 8.

382 **Result 2. Cooperation over time.** *With the ability to submit conditional strategies, for all group sizes the trend*
 383 *in cooperation level across 30 rounds does not decline, provided that the group marginal return is sufficiently*
 384 *high.*

385 Support for Result 2 comes from Figure 2 and Table 5. The pattern is clearly illustrated by Figure 2, where for
 386 Baseline we observe the usual trend of declining cooperation in public good experiments, while for Common
 387 commitment cooperation remains around the initial levels. If one partitions a session into initial, middle, and last
 388 rounds, and then compute the average cooperation, this pattern is confirmed (Table 5). In Baseline, the rate of
 389 cooperation drops between -4 and -31 percentage points between the first 10 and the last 10 rounds. By contrast,
 390 under Common commitment, cooperation oscillated in-between -2 and +6 percentage points – and there is no
 391 statistically significant difference between rounds 1 vs. 30 – with the noted exception of $n=15$, when cooperation
 392 drops 20 percentage points. The group dynamics in cooperation is also revealed by transitional matrices that map
 393 the number of cooperators in a group 0, 1,..., n in round t versus the same variable in round $t+1$ (Appendix C). The
 394 high empirical frequencies in some cells highlight which are the outcomes where the group tend to move to and
 395 the eventual presence of attracting points. Under Baseline, matrices drawn for each group size reveal that mutual
 396 defection is the strongest attractor. Under Common commitment, the pattern is quite different, as there generally
 397 exists at least two strong attractors, mutual cooperation and mutual defection. Nothing else appears prominent on
 398 the main diagonal of the transition matrix except for the largest group size of 15. In those treatments, other

399 attractors are one cooperator for $n=15$ and seven and thirteen cooperators for $n=15$ -high. This analysis is in line
400 with Result 2.

401

Figure 2. Average cooperation rates over time

Table 5: Cooperation over time by treatment

Group size	Baseline			Common commitment		
	First 10 rounds	Middle 10 rounds	Last 10 rounds	First 10 rounds	Middle 10 rounds	Last 10 rounds
2	85%	83%	81% ***	98%	99%	99%
3	67%	60%	51% ***	76%	80%	82%
6	47%	28%	16% ***	58%	54%	56%
15	32%	22%	15% ***	39%	27%	19% **
15-high	51%	39%	28% ***	67%	61%	65%

403 Notes: Statistical significance: *** = 0.01, ** = 0.05, * = 0.10 of a Wilcoxon signed-rank test about rejecting the null
404 hypothesis that the number of cooperators in a group is the same in round 1 vs. round 30 (the unit of observation is a group in a
405 session. No. obs.: 24, 23, 17, 8, 8 for Baseline; 24, 23, 16, 10, 8 for Common commitment).

406

407 **Result 3. Strategies adoption.** *A large majority of participants preferred conditional to unconditional strategies,*
408 *regardless of group size (68%-77%).*

409 Support for Result 3 comes from Table 6 and Figure 3. When conditional strategies were available, on average
410 only about one of four strategies adopted were unconditional, and that empirical share did not vary systematically
411 with group size: 31% ($n=2$), 24% ($n=3$), 23% ($n=6$), 23% ($n=15$), 25% ($n=15$ -high). Hence, the strong behavioral
412 attractiveness of conditional strategies did not diminish because of the complexity generated by large group sizes.
413 Given the rich strategy space, it is hard to exactly check which empirical strategy profiles were equilibrium one.
414 Recall that while in Baseline, "unconditional cooperation" is never part of an equilibrium strategy for self-
415 regarding agents, it can be in Common commitment. To clarify this point, consider separately equilibrium
416 outcomes supported by symmetric or asymmetric strategies. Under symmetric strategies, however, some
417 strategies are not equilibrium one: unconditional cooperation, and conditionally cooperative strategies subject to
418 the condition that too few others also cooperate (see Table 6). These latter strategies are individually unprofitable
419 in comparison to unconditional defection. To be more precise, for the design parameters there exists a minimum
420 subset of cooperators that makes individual cooperation more profitable than mutual defection (Table 6). Under
421 asymmetric strategies, the situation is different. Consider for instance in $n=3$ an unconditional cooperator along
422 with two other group members willing to contribute only if everyone else does. This applies more generally also
423 to what we call unprofitable conditional strategies." In the experiment, although larger groups register a lower
424 frequency of unconditional cooperators, it is counterbalanced by a bigger frequency of participants who are
425 willing to cooperate under weak conditions, who may have other-regarding preferences. Overall, out-of-
426 equilibrium strategies for self-regarding agents are at least 24% in Common commitment. This is a lower bound

427 that we can compare with the actual percentage of out-of-equilibrium strategies in Baseline (47%).¹⁰ In both
 428 treatments, these deviations entail pro-cooperative strategies.

429

Table 6. Strategy adoption in Common Commitment

	Group size				
	2	3	6	15	15-high
<i>Minimum subset of cooperators that makes individual cooperation more profitable than mutual defection</i>	2	2	4	9	4
Individual strategy:					
<i>Unconditional cooperation</i>	30,5%	11,8%	7,4%	4,0%	13,9%
2	68,7%	42,1%	7,0%	2,8%	6,8%
3		34,1%	8,0%	2,5%	3,5%
4			25,5%	3,0%	6,8%
5			15,9%	3,4%	6,3%
6			20,0%	5,3%	3,8%
7				3,8%	3,7%
8				6,8%	4,2%
9				11,3%	4,6%
10				9,1%	3,3%
11				8,4%	8,6%
12				3,7%	4,1%
13				3,2%	4,9%
14				2,9%	4,1%
15				10,1%	10,9%
<i>Unconditional defection</i>	0,8%	12,0%	16,2%	19,5%	10,5%
No. obs.	1440 (100%)	2070(100%)	2880(100%)	4500(100%)	3600(100%)

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Figure 3. Strategies adopted in Common commitment.

¹⁰ The lower bounds for the Common commitment are: 30.5% ($n=2$), 11.8% ($n=3$), 22.4% ($n=6$), 31.7% ($n=15$), 24.2% ($n=15$ -high).
 The exact percentages for Baseline are 83.2% ($n=2$), 59.3% ($n=3$), 30.6% ($n=6$), 23.1% ($n=15$), 39.6% ($n=15$ -high).

Notes: Common Commitment treatment only. Conditional strategies are divided into profitable and unprofitable depending on the minimum subset of cooperators that makes individual cooperation more profitable than mutual defection is 2 for $n=2$ and $n=3$, 4 for $n=6$ and $n=15$ High, 9 for $n=15$. For each group size, the first bar refers to the first 10 rounds in a session and the second bar to the last 10 rounds in a session.

In addition, Figure 3 shows the frequency of strategy adoption in Common commitment by clustering strategies into four types. Over the 30 rounds of interaction, there is only a limited amount of learning in strategy adoption. When comparing the first versus the last 10 rounds of a session, one observes two shifts: a stable or increasing share of conditional strategies of up to 10 percentage points, depending on group size, and a slight decline in non-equilibrium strategies (unconditional cooperation and unprofitable conditional strategies; except for $n=2$).

A way to understand group dynamics in the Common Commitment treatments is to look at strategy profiles for the group to identify possible social tipping points in group cooperation. Figure 4 illustrates through step functions the empirical frequencies of strategies for $n=15$ and $n=15$ -high that we have already presented in Table 6. The initial step in the graph records the frequency of unconditional cooperators, while the last step shows the unconditional defectors. The intermediate steps are the conditional cooperators, where the x-axis denotes the minimum threshold that triggers a participant to contribute to the public good. The threshold has been rescaled as share 0-100 of individuals in the group willing to contribute.

Figure 4. Empirical tipping point in group cooperation

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Hence, the step corresponding to a threshold of 80, for instance, shows how many extra participants are willing to contribute when 12 or more others contribute, while the corresponding y-axis value of the step function for the 80 threshold shows the total number of participants willing to contribute. Figure 4 enables us to identify potential tipping points in cooperation. In particular, consider the intersection of the step function for $n=15$ -high with the diagonal line in red, where the step function crosses the diagonal from above at a threshold around 50. This suggests the presence of a stable level of cooperation in the group at around 50%. Notice that the intersection for the $n=15$ is located close to the 0 threshold, at the initial step, which denotes the unconditional cooperators. This is an indication that group cooperation in $n=15$ may tumble down toward zero over time.

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Result 4. Volatility in outcomes. *With the ability to submit conditional strategies, there is a polarization in group outcomes and a simultaneous decline in earning inequality among individuals.*

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Support for Result 4 is in Tables 7 and 8. The frequency of partial cooperation in Common Commitment declines in comparison to Baseline, and the magnitude varies between -16 and -47 percentage points depending on the group size. For instance, for $n=15$ the combined frequency of full defection and full cooperation accounts for 7% of group outcomes in Baseline vs. 42% in Common Commitment. A similar pattern is present for smaller groups

(Table 7). This polarization in group outcomes is the likely consequence of the widespread adoption of conditional strategies.¹¹

A positive aspect of the adoption of conditional strategies is a more egalitarian division of earnings in all group sizes. When considering the standard deviation of overall individual earnings within each group, we report higher equality in the Common Commitment vs. the Baseline treatment for all group sizes (Table 7). For instance, in $n=6$ the SD is 1.68 in Baseline and 0.83 in Common Commitment.

A negative pattern of the adoption of conditional strategies is an increase in the volatility over time of group outcomes especially for larger groups.¹² When measured in terms of variance in the number of cooperators in a group, the values are, for instance, 5.82 vs. 26.84 in $n=15$ and 6.76 vs. 20.33 in $n=15$ -high (Table 8). The underlying mechanism for the volatility in Common Commitment seems to be the drastic jumps in the number of cooperators in a group generated by trembling hand behavior combined with conditional strategies (Figure 2).

Table 7: Polarization in group outcomes: data and theory

Group size		Full defection	Partial cooperation	Full cooperation	No. obs. or share
2	Baseline	8.3%	16.9%	74.7%	720
	Common commitment	1.4%	0.3%	98.3%	720
	<i>Eq.strategy share</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.22</i>
3	Baseline	15.8%	49.3%	34.9%	690
	Common commitment	14.2%	15.7%	70.1%	690
	<i>Eq.strategy share</i>	<i>0.06</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.22</i>
6	Baseline	21.0%	78.6%	0.4%	510
	Common commitment	29.8%	31.7%	38.5%	480
	<i>Eq.strategy share</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>0.03</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>0.13</i>
15	Baseline	7.1%	92.9%	0.0%	240
	Common commitment	38.0%	58.3%	3.7%	300
	<i>Eq.strategy share</i>	<i>0.02</i>	<i>0.03</i>	<i>0.03</i>	<i>0.08</i>
15-high	Baseline	0.4%	99.6%	0.0%	240
	Common commitment	3.3%	74.2%	22.5%	240
	<i>Eq.strategy share</i>	<i>0.02</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>0.06</i>	<i>0.13</i>

Notes: Frequency of empirical group outcomes (%), where the unit of observation is a group in a round. The equilibrium strategy share is the fraction of equilibrium strategies for Common Commitment out of all possible strategies. Recall that in Baseline the only equilibrium strategy profile is full defection.

¹¹ We report that -- in comparison to Baseline -- the frequency of a full cooperation outcome always increases in Common commitment, while the frequency of a full defection outcome declines for $n=2,3$ and increases for $n>3$.

¹² For $n=2$, volatility is especially low in Common Commitment because of the high cooperation level that are up to the boundary of 100% cooperation.

Table 8: Individual inequality and cooperation volatility

Group Size	Individual earning inequality (S.D.)		Number of cooperators in a group (Variance)	
	Baseline	Common Commitment	Baseline	Common Commitment
2	0.47	0.02	0.39	0.06
3	0.95	0.56	1.19	1.15
6	1.68	0.83	1.97	6.84
15	2.04	1.26	5.82	26.84
15 high	2.60	2.16	6.76	20.33

Notes: The earnings inequalities are standard deviations calculated for individuals in the same group and then averaged across groups.

Result 5. Impact of nudges. Targeted individual messages enhance cooperation by emphasizing potential individual gains.

Support for Result 5 is in Table 9 and 10. Nudges took the form of customized pro-cooperative messages in the Common Commitment treatment. The frequency and impact of these nudges are summarized in Table 9. In terms of frequency, between 6% and 9% of individual choices received a message, with the exception of $n=2$, where there were very few messages (0.6%) as most groups were already at full cooperation. The evidence suggests that nudging successfully boosted cooperation levels. How did a participant react when receiving a message? In 49%-100% of instances she submitted a *more* cooperative strategy in the following round. She submitted a *less* cooperative strategy only in few instances (0%-7%). We also present a regression analysis in Table 10 that uses as dependent variable whether a participant in round t submitted a more cooperative strategy than in $t-1$. The impact on the individual who receives a message is highly statistically significant for all group sizes, even when controlling for the aggregate cooperation level, a time trend, and session fixed effects.

Table 9: Summary statistics about nudges

Group Size	% individual actions that received a nudge	No. of observations	Strategy in round t vs. $t-1$ (when a nudge was received in $t-1$)		
			Less cooperative	Stayed the same	More cooperative
2	0.6%	9/1392	0%	0%	100%
3	8.3%	167/2001	7%	27%	66%
6	7.9%	219/2784	6%	35%	59%

15	6.5%	282/4350	7%	44%	49%
15 high	7.5%	261/3480	7%	29%	64%

Table 10: Regression results about nudges

<i>Dep. Var.:</i> 1= individual strategy in t is more cooperative than in $t-1$, 0= otherwise	2	3	6	15	15 High
Nudge received in $t-1$	Perfect correlation	1.596 (0.111)***	0.997 (0.092)***	0.469 (0.079)***	0.993 (0.155)***
Number of contributors in the group in t	0.051 (0.243)	0.116 (0.035)***	0.060 (0.010)***	0.027 (0.004)***	
Round	-0.016 (0.007)**	-0.014 (0.004)***	-0.011 (0.003)***	-0.004 (0.002)	-0.009 (0.003)***
Constant	-1.526 (0.4963)***	-1.100 (0.119)***	-1.029 (0.085)***	-0.652 (0.066)***	-0.515 (0.064)***
Number of observations	1383	2001	2784	4350	3480

Notes: Probit marginal effects for Common Commitment treatments. Session fixed effects included but not shown in the table. The dep. var. is related to the "More cooperative" column of Table 9.

7 Discussion and Conclusions

Does cooperation increase when allowing individuals to condition their cooperation to others doing the same? We study this question through a laboratory experiment with small and large groups. We find that the prospects for cooperation are substantially enhanced by the possibility to submit conditional strategies, regardless of group size, provided that the returns to investing in the public good are sufficiently high. When this condition is satisfied, cooperation is sustained over time even in large groups, with stable contributions made from a majority of subjects up until the very last round of interaction. This trend of unwavering cooperation in large groups does not hold in the corresponding baseline treatment in which only unconditional cooperation is allowed, where we report the commonly observed unravelling of cooperation. The intuition behind the appeal of conditional cooperation is simple, as such strategies leverage the logic of reciprocity and the reassurance that conditional commitments cannot be taken advantage of by free riders, which is a major obstacle to unconditional cooperation. In more formal terms, the opportunity to submit conditional strategies can transform a social dilemma into a coordination game, and the actual use of conditional strategies neutralizes the negative impact of the strategic uncertainty of cooperative action. These findings and insights can be leveraged when drawing up conditional cooperation

519 schemes in multilateral treaties about global public goods. Specifically, the implementation of conditional
520 strategies may facilitate cooperation among governments that are concerned with freeriding when negotiating
521 international treaties to address climate change. The history of climate negotiations suggests that such concerns
522 have been major roadblocks, with so-called “non-Annex I” countries from the Global South demanding
523 reassurances about mitigation commitments from remaining countries, and industrialized Annex I countries
524 (notably the U.S.) advancing similar requests towards industrializing economies such as China on the grounds of
525 competitiveness concerns (Aklin, Buntaine, & Mildenerger, 2020). Recent evidence suggests that, while trade
526 flows indeed create competitive economic pressures that may undermine climate action, such pressures are
527 dampened when trade partners also commit (Rowan, 2025). The author concludes that “states have bought into
528 the Paris framework and are making progress through its ratchet mechanism. While not every state has committed
529 to strong targets, a crucial subset has, and they are pulling others with them. [... States] were more likely to
530 commit to stronger targets when their political peers had ambitious targets”. Here we provide additional evidence
531 that, so long as the benefits of cooperation are not too modest, agreements that are built around conditional
532 commitments hold potential for successfully addressing cooperation challenges.

533 The introduction of conditional strategies expands the equilibrium set and has the behavioral effect of enabling
534 coordination on a cooperative outcome. Across group sizes ranging between 2 and 15, we document a boost in
535 cooperation relative to conditions in which subjects were restricted to unconditional strategies. Its magnitude,
536 however, varies considerably, ranging from +4 through +25 percentage points depending on the treatment (Figure
537 1). We now discuss three conjectures about the possible mechanisms at work. The first conjecture is about the
538 numerosity of the minimum subset of cooperators that makes individual cooperation more profitable than mutual
539 defection (Figure 3), a value which is tied to the individual return from cooperation. Put simply, the higher the
540 return, the higher the expected cooperation rate. The second conjecture is that larger groups find it harder to
541 coordinate, which would weaken the success of conditional strategies in increasing cooperation among large
542 groups. The third conjecture is about the dependence of the ability to achieve a cooperative outcome on the
543 difficulty of selecting an equilibrium strategy, due to the variable numerosity of cooperative equilibrium strategy
544 profiles across treatments (Table 7).

545 A clean way to assess the above conjectures is to focus on the comparative statics of just three treatments – $n=6$,
546 15, 15-high – because they enable bilateral comparisons where only one parameter changes: n or γ . In particular,
547 these three treatments enable to disentangle the independent impact of the two dimensions that vary when group
548 size changes: individual/group marginal returns and coordination issues. The individual return conjecture predicts
549 that the cooperation rate will be the same in $n=6$ and $n=15$ -high, while it will be lower in $n=15$., which is what we
550 observe in the data when we measure success in terms of the percentage point increment in average cooperation
551 level between Baseline and Common Commitment (Figure 1). The coordination complexity conjecture predicts

552 instead that cooperation will be higher in $n=6$, compared to both $n=15$ and $n=15$ -high, which is not supported by
553 the data. The third conjecture, about cooperative equilibrium selection being harder the more the available
554 equilibria, predicts that cooperation will be highest in $n=15$ -high, followed by $n=6$ and $n=15$ with the lowest rate,
555 which enjoys only partial support.

556 When we extend the analyses to all five Baseline-Common commitment comparisons, the conclusions are more
557 ambiguous. One possible reason is that in Baseline three out of four groups for $n=2$ were already at full
558 cooperation, hence there was no room for improvement. For $n=3$, this occurred for about one group out of three
559 (Table 7). The observed ranking of all treatments is $6 \cong 15\text{-high} > 3 > 2 > 15$. The individual return conjecture predicts
560 $2 > 3 > 6 = 15\text{-high} > 15$, and its accuracy rests on the above-mentioned possible censoring in the experiment with
561 $n=2, 3$. Based on the evidence in Table 7, one may argue that the increments for $n=2, 3$ are comparable to those
562 for $n=6$. The coordination conjecture predicts $2 > 3 > 6 > 15 = 15\text{-high}$, which can justify its gap with observed values
563 because of a censoring for $n=2, 3$, as above, but hardly when it comes to the large difference between $n=15$ and
564 $n=15$ -high. Finally, the coordination complexity conjecture predicts $3 > 2 > 15\text{-high} > 6 > 15$, which enjoys only
565 partial support.

566 Taken together, the evidence suggests that multiple channels are at work, but among the three that we consider
567 above individual returns play an important role. It becomes critical for external validity to assess what is a
568 reasonable estimate of this parameter in the field. In fact, for a marginal individual return of 0.12 as in $n=15$, the
569 Common Commitment has similar cooperation levels as the Baseline. For the Ozone layer treaty, EPA estimates
570 a cost-benefit ratio for the US of 1:65. For climate policy, the Stern review from 2006 suggests a range for γ of
571 **2.5 - 20** (Stern 2007). The costs of achieving stabilisation between 500 and 550 ppm CO₂e are around 1% of
572 global GDP, if we start to take strong action now (Stern later revised the cost to 2% in 2008). The Review estimates
573 that if we don't act, the overall costs and risks of climate change will be equivalent to losing at least 5% of global
574 GDP each year, now and forever. If a wider range of risks and impacts is taken into account, the estimates of
575 damage could rise to 20% of GDP or more.¹³ We need to consider also the number of countries as the individual
576 return is γ/n . The Paris Agreement was negotiated by 196 parties, and we divide γ by 196 it will become hopelessly
577 small. More generally, is an experiment with $n=15$ large enough to be meaningful for an international treaty? In
578 reference to climate mitigation, consider that the top 15 emitting countries comprise 71% of emissions in 2023,
579 and that sums up to 78% if we treat EU as one decision maker.

580 Lastly, we mention some limitations and possible extensions of the present study. An implicit assumption in
581 Common Commitment is that decisions, including conditional strategies, are legally binding. Hence, the decision-

¹³ Estimates by Nordhaus (2017) for +4°C, and by Burke et al. (2015) are also compatible with 4.5.

582 maker cannot later renege and cooperate less than they initially declared. This design's feature may be relevant,
583 and it is an open question whether the reported success in terms of increased cooperation would reduce if the
584 initial decision were a simple promise and there was no third-party institution to do the enforcement. The
585 robustness of the results could be tested by modifying this design feature in the lab.

586 Asymmetries and inequalities among group members are a major feature of field settings, while in the lab all
587 participants are identical in terms of incentives and roles. This dimension is especially evident for countries
588 addressing climate mitigation. The purpose of this study was to establish a clean empirical regularity under the
589 simplest conditions. Existing experiments suggest that individual heterogeneity usually damages cooperation,
590 although it is unclear if it weakens the effects of adding conditional strategies. Finally, do our results hinge on the
591 presence of nudges? Although they influence individual behavior, we conjecture that removing nudges may not
592 alter qualitatively the results.

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706 **Appendices**

707 **Appendix A: Experimental Instructions (Original in Italian)**

708 **A.1 Instructions for the Baseline treatment**

709 Welcome! In this session you will be asked to make economic decisions. Please follow the instructions carefully.
710 You will later be asked to answer some questions regarding their content.

711 Your earnings depend on your choices as well as the choices of other participants. Your earnings will be expressed
712 in “points.” For each point gotten during this session, you will receive a payment of 4 euro cents. In any case, you
713 will receive a minimum payment of 5 euros. Payment will be made privately via PayPal.

714 Any form of communication among participants is prohibited. Should you have any questions, please feel free to
715 raise your hand, and we will come to your desk to clarify your doubts. Detailed instructions can be found below.

716 **Today’s activities**

717 Participants in this room will receive an identification number -ID- from 1 to 24 and will be randomly divided
718 into groups of six. Your ID and your group will be the same throughout the session.

719 Today’s session consists of **30 rounds**.

720 At the beginning of each round, each participant receives an endowment of 10 points and must make a choice:
721 Where to put one’s own endowment? The participant can choice to put it all into an INDIVIDIAL account or into
722 a GROUP account. More precisely, she can choose one of the following options:

- 723 1. Put all the endowment into the GROUP account.
- 724 2. Put all the endowment into the INDIVIDIAL account.

725 Choices are made simultaneously by group members. So, when you choose, you cannot see what choice the others
726 have made. You will only see their choice at the end of the round.

727 Specifically, the choice will be made as shown in the screen below:

728
729 Are there any questions?

730 Now let’s see how earnings are calculated.

731 **Earnings**

732 If you put your endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account, it generates 10 points of earnings for you.

733 If you instead put the endowment into the GROUP account, it generates 3 points for each group member (0.3*10
734 points), including you. So, your choice generates in the group earnings totaling 18 points (0,3 * 10 points * 6
735 members). Your earnings in each round will then be calculated as follows:

736
$$\text{Your earnings} = \text{points put by you into the INDIVIDUAL account (0 or 10)}$$

737
$$+ 0.3 * (\text{points put by everyone in the GROUP account})$$

738 There may be 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 or 60 points in the GROUP account depending on the participants' choices. If
739 everyone puts their own endowment into the GROUP account, then each group member earns 18 points (=0,3 *
740 60). Conversely, if everyone puts their own endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account, then each group member
741 earns 10 points.

742 After everyone has completed their choice, a screen with the results like the one below will appear:

RISULTATI per il periodo : 1 su 3 **Il tuo ID: 2**

ID	Scelta di ognuno	Guadagni di ognuno^
1	GRUPPO	
2 (tu)	GRUPPO	15
3	INDIVIDUALE	
4	GRUPPO	
5	GRUPPO	
6	GRUPPO	

^I tuoi guadagni in questo periodo = 0 nel tuo Conto Individuale + (50 nel Conto di Gruppo)* 0,3 = 15

Storico dei risultati

Periodo	I tuoi risultati	Risultato del gruppo (Numero di dotazioni assegnate al conto di gruppo, tu compreso).	I tuoi guadagni
1	GRUPPO	5	15

OK

743

744

745 At the top of the screen, you can see your choice as ID 2 and the **choices of each** of the other members of your
746 group. Now you can also see the **result of everyone**, in terms of the actual destination of your endowment
747 wheatear into the INDIVIDUAL or GROUP account. Also, you can see your earnings in the current round. At
748 the end of the session your earnings from all rounds are summed up. Finally, at the bottom of the screen, you can
749 see a table with the history of your results from previous rounds.

750 Are there any questions?

751 Now we will use an example to explain how the choices of everyone in the group are combined in order to
752 determine the result.

753 *Example:*

754 Consider the case illustrated in the figure where five group members, including you, put the endowment into the
755 GROUP account, and where one member puts the endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account. In this example,
756 you earn 15 points. Your earnings are the sum of 0 points into the INDIVIDUAL account plus $0.3 \cdot 50 = 15$ points
757 from the endowments put into the GROUP account.

758 The person with ID 3 who has put the endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account earns 25 points, which is the
759 sum of 10 points into her INDIVIDUAL account plus $0.3 \cdot 50 = 15$ points from the endowments put into the
760 GROUP account.

761 Are there any questions?
762

763 **A.2 Instructions for the Common commitment treatment (CC)**

764 Welcome! In this session you will be asked to make economic decisions. Please follow the instructions carefully.
765 You will later be asked to answer some questions regarding their content.

766 Your earnings depend on your choices as well as the choices of other participants. Your earnings will be expressed
767 in “points.” For each point gotten during this session, you will receive a payment of 4 euro cents. In any case, you
768 will receive a minimum payment of 5 euros. Payment will be made privately via PayPal.

769 Any form of communication among participants is prohibited. Should you have any questions, please feel free to
770 raise your hand, and we will come to your desk to clarify your doubts. Detailed instructions can be found below.

771 **Today’s activities**

772 Participants in this room will receive an identification number -ID- from 1 to 24 and will be randomly divided
773 into groups of six. Your ID and your group will be the same throughout the session.

774 Today’s session consists of **30 rounds**.

775 At the beginning of each round, each participant receives an endowment of 10 points and must make a choice:
776 Where to put one’s own endowment? The participant can choose to put it all into an INDIVIDIAL account or
777 into a GROUP account. More precisely, she can choose one of the following options:

- 778 1. Put all the endowment into the GROUP account.
- 779 2. Put all the endowment into the GROUP account, ONLY IF ALL other members of the group do so.
- 780 3. Put all the endowment into the GROUP account, ONLY IF AT LEAST FOUR other members of the
781 group do so.
- 782 4. Put all the endowment into the GROUP account, ONLY IF AT LEAST THREE other members of the
783 group do so.
- 784 5. Put all the endowment into the GROUP account, ONLY IF AT LEAST TWO other members of the
785 group do so.
- 786 6. Put all the endowment into the GROUP account, ONLY IF AT LEAST ONE other member of the group
787 does so.
- 788 7. Put all the endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account.

789 Choices are made simultaneously by group members. Therefore, **when you choose, you cannot see what choice**
790 **the others have made**. You will only see their choice at the end of the round.

791 You may have noticed that in options 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 your endowment could end up in either the GROUP
792 account or in the INDIVIAL account hinging on what choices others make.
793

794 Consider *Example 1* shown below, where everyone makes the same choice, which is to put the endowment in the
795 GROUP account ONLY IF EVERYONE else does:

796
797

798

ID	Scelta individuale	Risultato individuale	Guadagno individuale^
7	GRUPPO SOLO SE TUTTI	GRUPPO	
8	GRUPPO SOLO SE TUTTI	GRUPPO	
9 (tu)	GRUPPO SOLO SE TUTTI	GRUPPO	18
10	GRUPPO SOLO SE TUTTI	GRUPPO	
11	GRUPPO SOLO SE TUTTI	GRUPPO	
12	GRUPPO SOLO SE TUTTI	GRUPPO	

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807 In this example, the outcome is that everyone puts the endowment into the GROUP account because it satisfies
808 simultaneously the conditions expressed by everyone. To this end, the computer verifies ex-post that the
809 conditions are met. We will return to this in a moment to explain with other examples how individual choices are
810 combined in order to determine the outcome.

811 Specifically, the choice will be made as shown in the screen below:

Dove vuoi mettere la tua dotazione?

- Nel conto di GRUPPO
- Nel conto di GRUPPO, SOLO SE ALMENO UNO degli altri membri del gruppo lo fa.
- Nel conto di GRUPPO, SOLO SE ALMENO DUE degli altri membri del gruppo lo fa
- Nel conto di GRUPPO, SOLO SE ALMENO TRE degli altri membri del gruppo lo fa
- Nel conto di GRUPPO, SOLO SE ALMENO QUATTRO degli altri membri del gruppo lo fa
- Nel conto di GRUPPO, SOLO SE TUTTI gli altri membri del gruppo lo fanno
- Nel conto di INDIVIDUALE

OK

812

813 Are there any questions?

814 Let us now see how earnings are computed.

815 **Earnings**

816 If you put your endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account, it generates 10 points of earnings for you.

817 If, otherwise, you put the endowment into the GROUP account, it generates 3 points for each group member
818 (0.3*10 points), including you. Therefore, your choice generates in the group earnings totaling 18 points (0,3 *
819 10 points * 6 members). Your earnings in each round will then be computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 820 \text{ Your earnings} &= \text{points put by you into the INDIVIDUAL account (0 or 10)} \\ 821 &+ 0,3 * (\text{points put by everyone in the GROUP account}) \end{aligned}$$

822 There may be 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 or 60 points in the GROUP account depending on the participants' choices. If
823 everyone puts their own endowment into the GROUP account, then each group member earns 18 points (=0,3 *
824 60). Conversely, if everyone puts their own endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account, then each group member
825 earns 10 points.

826 After everyone has completed their choice, a screen with the results like the one below will appear:

RISULTATI per il periodo : 1 su 3 **Il tuo ID: 2**

ID	Scelta di ognuno	Risultato di ognuno	Guadagni di ognuno^
1	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	INDIVIDUALE	
2 (tu)	GRUPPO SOLO SE TUTTI	INDIVIDUALE	10
3	INDIVIDUALE	INDIVIDUALE	
4	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	INDIVIDUALE	
5	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	INDIVIDUALE	
6	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	INDIVIDUALE	

*^I tuoi guadagni in questo periodo = 10 nel tuo Conto Individuale + (0 nel Conto di Gruppo) *0,3 = 10*

Opportunità mancata! Se avessi scelto GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO QUATTRO degli altri membri del gruppo lo fa, i tuoi guadagni di questo periodo sarebbero stati superiori di 5 punti.

Storico dei risultati

Periodo	I tuoi risultati	Risultato del gruppo (Numero di dotazioni assegnate al conto di gruppo, tu compreso).	I tuoi guadagni
1	INDIVIDUALE	0	10

OK

827

828 At the top of the screen, you are ID 2, and you can see your choice and the **choices of each** of the other members
829 of your group. Now you can see the **result of everyone**, in terms of the actual destination of your endowment
830 wheatear into the INDIVIDUAL or GROUP account. Also, you can see your earnings in the current round. At
831 the end of the session your earnings from all rounds are summed up. Finally, at the bottom of the screen, you can
832 see a table with a history of your results from previous rounds.

833 Now we will use an example to explain how the choices of everyone in the group are combined in order to
834 determine the outcome.

835 *Example 2:*

836 The screen above illustrates an example: you are **ID 2** and have chosen to put your endowment into the GROUP
837 account **ONLY IF EVERYONE** in the group does so. The column “Everyone’s result” indicates, nevertheless,
838 that the actual destination of your endowment is the INDIVIDUAL account. **Why?**

839 Because not everyone else in the group has put their endowment into the GROUP account, contradicting the
840 condition you have expressed for you to put the endowment into the GROUP account. Specifically, the screen
841 above shows that the person with ID 3 wants to put the endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account under any
842 circumstances, i.e. regardless of what others do. The condition that you set to put the endowment into the GROUP
843 account is therefore not met. This explains your result.

844 Continuing with the same example, look at the choice of ID 1, ID 4, ID 5 and ID 6: they want to put the endowment
845 into the GROUP account ONLY IF AT LEAST FOUR OTHER members did so. As we have seen, both ID 2
846 (you) and ID 3 put the endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account, so this condition is contradicted. In conclusion,
847 everyone's endowment will go into the INDIVIDUAL account.

848 Are there any questions?

849 In example 2, everyone earns 10 points, including you.

850 Automatic feedback

851 Example 3: In example 2 you could have increased your earnings if you had made another choice. In fact, in the
852 example you are ID 2 and if instead of demanding that EVERYONE puts the endowment into the group account,
853 you had chosen that AT LEAST FOUR OTHER group members do so, the result would have been as follows:

854

ID	Scelta individuale	Risultato individuale	Guadagno individuale^
1	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	GRUPPO	
2 (tu)	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	GRUPPO	15
3	INDIVIDUALE	INDIVIDUALE	
4	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	GRUPPO	
5	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	GRUPPO	
6	GRUPPO SOLO SE ALMENO ALTRI QUATTRO	GRUPPO	

861

862 If you had made this choice, your earnings would have been 15 points instead of 10. In the new Example 3
863 illustrated in the above table, ID 3 puts the endowment into the INDIVIDUAL account anyway. Despite this, all
864 the other five group members now put the endowment into the GROUP account. Recall that everyone's condition
865 was that AT LEAST OTHER FOUR put the endowment into the GROUP account. Since the condition is met,
866 the endowment goes to the GROUP account.

867 How are your earnings calculated? Your earnings are the sum of 0 points into the INDIVIDIAL account plus
868 $0,3*50 = 15$ points of all the endowments put into the GROUP account.

869 Whenever similar situations occur in which there is an opportunity for a participant to increase her own earnings
870 in this way, automatic feedback will appear with the words "**Missed Opportunity**" (see the screen above
871 Example 2)

872 In this Example 3, ID 3 would earn 25 points, the sum of 10 points into the INDIVIDUAL account plus $0.3*50 =$
873 15 points from the endowments put into the GROUP account.

874 Are there any questions?

875

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Appendix B: Additional tables and Figures

878

Figure B1. Number of cooperators by group size

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Notes: Empirical frequencies on the vertical axis. CC= Common commitment.

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892 Figure B2. Average cooperation rates over time by single group, n=6

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895 Figure B3. Average cooperation rates over time by single group, n=15

896

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902 Appendix C: Transition matrices

904 When discussing Result 2, the main Results section refers to **transition matrices**. This appendix presents
 905 the methodology and ten tables. How are the transition matrices built? for each $n=2, 3, 6, 15, 15\text{-high}$ we
 906 consider group outcomes in round t versus group outcomes in round $t+1$. Consider the total number of
 907 cooperators in a given round of the Common commitment treatment (the same is later done for the
 908 Baseline treatment). For each line (“From:” in the tables below), we set the number of observations to
 909 100% and match it with what happens to the group in the following round in terms of number of
 910 cooperators (“To:”). The bold percentage denotes the attractors, which indicate the tendency to
 911 systematically shift, or not, to a new cell of the transition matrix, or remain there. As a convention adopted
 912 simply for the reading of the tables, if the percentage on the line is above 50%, we say that there is just
 913 one “attractor;” otherwise, we still highlight all cells with percentages above 20% [in bold, in case this
 914 “attractors” they exist. This convention is behavioral and not linked to any theoretical concept.

915 If we look at the main diagonal, we see as attractors mutual cooperation for all group size n in Common
 916 commitment; we see mutual defection for all n except 15-high. Nothing else, except just one cooperator
 917 for $n=15$ and 7 or 13 cooperators for $n= 15\text{-high}$.

921 Table C1. Transition matrix for n=2 -- Common commitment

		To:			Total
		0	1	2	
From:	0			100%	100%
	1	50%		50%	100%
	2	1%		99%	100%

922

923 Table C2. Transition matrix for n=3 -- Common commitment

		To:				Total
		0	1	2	3	
From:	0	28%	2%	21%	49%	100%
	1	29%	19%	14%	38%	100%
	2	25%	5%	24%	46%	100%
	3	9%	3%	8%	80%	100%

924

925 Table C3. Transition matrix for n=6 -- Common commitment

		To:						Total	
		0	1	2	3	4	5		6
From:	0	39%	5%	4%	1%	9%	14%	28%	100%
	1	32%	6%			3%	13%	45%	100%
	2	48%	10%		5%	5%	5%	29%	100%
	3	17%	17%	17%	17%	8%		25%	100%
	4	26%	12%		9%	6%	15%	32%	100%
	5	38%	4%	10%	4%	8%	15%	21%	100%
	6	19%	7%	5%	1%	6%	8%	54%	100%

926

927 Table C4. Transition matrix for n=15 -- Common commitment

		To:														Total		
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13		14	15
From:	0	47%	8%	2%	5%	2%	6%	1%			4%	6%	10%	5%	4%	2%	1%	100%
	1	29%	26%	10%	10%	5%			0%	2%				5%	7%	2%	5%	100%
	2	13%	20%					7%		7%		7%	7%	20%	20%			100%
	3	43%	14%	7%			7%		7%				7%	7%			7%	100%
	4	13%	50%	13%		25%												100%
	5	50%		33%									17%					100%
	6	25%	25%						25%				25%					100%
	7	67%	33%															100%
	8		50%	25%	25%													100%
	9	33%	17%		17%									17%			17%	100%
	10	25%	13%	13%					13%				13%		13%		13%	100%

11	61%	17%	4%	4%			4%	4%					4%				100%
12	42%	16%		5%								21%	11%			5%	100%
13	33%	7%	7%		7%		13%		7%	13%	13%						100%
14			33%	33%									33%				100%
15	27%	9%			9%		9%		9%				9%			27%	100%

928

929 Table C5. Transition matrix for n=15-high -- Common commitment

		To:																	
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	Total	
From:	0	13%									13%			13%	25%	13%	25%	100%	
	1												33%	33%		33%		100%	
	2						17%			17%			17%	17%		17%	17%	100%	
	3			11%		11%		11%		22%	11%					11%	22%	100%	
	4					17%							17%		17%	33%	17%	100%	
	5	6%					18%		12%	6%		6%	18%	12%	6%		18%	100%	
	6	7%	7%			13%	7%	7%		20%		13%			7%		13%	7%	100%
	7			6%	6%		17%			22%		11%		6%	6%	6%	22%	100%	
	8	7%			7%		14%	14%	7%	7%				7%	7%	14%	14%	100%	
	9	6%		6%			6%	17%	17%	17%			6%		6%		22%	100%	
	10						29%	14%		14%	14%						29%	100%	
	11		6%	6%	13%	6%	13%	13%	13%			6%	6%		6%		13%	100%	
	12					8%	17%		17%			8%	8%	8%	8%	17%	8%	100%	
	13			7%			7%	7%		13%	7%	7%	7%	7%	27%	7%	7%	100%	
	14	6%		6%		6%	6%	6%		6%	12%		6%	18%	6%	6%	18%	100%	
	15	4%	2%		2%		2%	4%	8%	4%	14%	2%	8%		2%	2%	47%	100%	

930

931

932 Table C6. Transition matrix for n=2 -- Baseline

		To:			
		0	1	2	Total
From:	0	48%	41%	11%	100%
	1	28%	47%	25%	100%
	2	1%	8%	92%	100%

933

934 Table C7. Transition matrix for n=3-- Baseline

		To:				
		0	1	2	3	Total
From:	0	42%	44%	7%	7%	100%
	1	30%	41%	23%	6%	100%
	2	10%	31%	46%	12%	100%
	3		4%	14%	82%	100%

935

936

937

938 Table C8. Transition matrix for n=6 -- Baseline

		To:																
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	Total
From:	0	36%	14%	29%	14%		7%											100%
	1	26%	38%	21%	10%	5%	0%											100%
	2	6%	35%	18%	24%	6%	6%		6%									100%
	3		13%	28%	23%	26%	5%	3%		3%								100%
	4		11%	9%	20%	39%	7%	9%	5%									100%
	5		5%	11%	16%	37%	21%		5%		5%							100%
	6			8%	17%	17%	8%	17%	17%	8%	8%							100%
	7				7%	29%	14%	21%	21%	7%	0%							100%
	8				17%	17%			17%		33%	17%						100%
	9					17%	33%		17%	17%	17%							100%
	10						33%	33%					33%					100%
	11						50%		50%									100%
	12																	na
	13																	na
	14																	na
	15																	na

939

940

941

942 Table C9. Transition matrix for n=15 -- Baseline

943

		To:																
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	Total
From:	0	36%	14%	29%	14%		7%											100%
	1	26%	38%	21%	10%	5%	0%											100%
	2	6%	35%	18%	24%	6%	6%		6%									100%
	3		13%	28%	23%	26%	5%	3%		3%								100%
	4		11%	9%	20%	39%	7%	9%	5%									100%
	5		5%	11%	16%	37%	21%		5%		5%							100%
	6			8%	17%	17%	8%	17%	17%	8%	8%							100%
	7				7%	29%	14%	21%	21%	7%	0%							100%
	8				17%	17%			17%		33%	17%						100%
	9					17%	33%		17%	17%	17%							100%
	10						33%	33%					33%					100%
	11						50%		50%									100%
	12																	na
	13																	na
	14																	na
	15																	na

944

945

946

947 Table C10. Transition matrix for n=15-high -- Baseline

		To:																	
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	Total	
From:	0	100%															100%		
	1	33%	33%	33%															100%
	2	13%		38%	13%	19%		13%	6%								100%		
	3	6%		28%	11%	17%	17%	6%	6%	6%	6%							100%	
	4	13%			13%	20%	27%	7%	3%	13%	3%							100%	
	5	15%				31%	36%	13%	3%	3%								100%	
	6	7%			10%	13%	13%	13%	27%	10%	3%	3%						100%	
	7	4%			17%		21%	17%	13%	21%	4%	4%						100%	
	8	8%				4%	12%	23%	23%	12%	8%	12%							100%
	9	27%							18%	23%	23%	5%	5%						100%
	10	17%								50%	17%	17%						100%	
	11	25%									38%	13%	25%					100%	
	12	50%										50%					100%		
	13	100%															100%		
	14																na		
	15																na		

948

949 **Appendix D: Common Commitment Equilibrium Analysis**

950 For the game implemented in the common commitment treatment, we present below the characteristics of the
 951 strategy profiles that will constitute equilibria for each type of outcome — full cooperation, partial cooperation,
 952 and full defection.

953 ***Full cooperation***

954 Under full cooperation one can discard all profiles containing at least one “unconditional defection” strategy.
 955 Next, notice that partial cooperation outcomes where the number of cooperators is equal to (or larger than)
 956 $f(\gamma) := \lceil n(\gamma - 1)/\gamma \rceil$ yields equal (or larger) benefits when defecting, compared to cooperating in a full
 957 cooperation outcome. For this reason, a full cooperation equilibrium preempts the possibility of partial
 958 cooperation outcomes of size greater or equal than $f(\gamma)$ as a result of any deviation to another strategy. This
 959 means that the conditional strategy $k = \lceil n(\gamma - 1)/\gamma \rceil - 1$ will not be part of any equilibrium profile here—
 960 except when the profits from partial cooperation given by $f(\gamma)$ match exactly those from full cooperation. Under
 961 these circumstances, players are indifferent. Example 2 attempts to clarify the logic.

963 *Suppose $n = 15$, $e = 10$, while γ varies to capture three scenarios of increasing magnitude of group return from*
 964 *contributing to the public good. Namely, $\gamma' = 1.8$, $\gamma'' = 4.5$ and $\gamma''' = 5$. In the first case, $f(\gamma') = 7$, meaning*
 965 *that the players earn 18 each under full cooperation, while under the partial cooperation outcome where 7 players*
 966 *cooperate, defectors earn 18.4 each. And since the defectors' payoff (see expression (1) of the experimental*
 967 *design section) is an increasing function on the number of cooperators, a partial cooperation outcome whose size*
 968 *ranges from 7 to 14 is invariably preferred for a defector than the full cooperation payoff. Then, in order for a*
 969 *full-cooperation strategy profile to be an equilibrium, it must be pivoting-proof by individual deviations toward*
 970 *a partial cooperation whose outcome size comprises at least 7 cooperators (8 defectors). For instance, the*
 971 *strategy profile (6,6,6,6,6,6,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,15), whose structure leads to the full cooperation outcome, is*
 972 *a pivoting-proof profile^{†††}. A player cannot deviate from her current strategy in order to alter the outcome and*
 973 *be better off while keeping the others' strategies constant.*

974 *We now consider $\gamma'' = 4.5$, which captures a situation of a more appealing public good with larger incentives to*
 975 *contribute (the MPCR increases from .12 to .3). Here the partial cooperation outcome, with size of at least*
 976 *$f(\gamma'') = 12$, gives the players better payoffs when defecting than when fully cooperating. Therefore, an*
 977 *equilibrium profile is set by strategies that deter individual deviations that turn out in partial cooperation of size*
 978 *12, 13 or 14.*

979 *Lastly, take γ''' , we have that $f(\gamma''') = f(\gamma'')$. However, under γ''' , the partial-cooperation outcome of size 12*
 980 *yields exactly the same payoff as the full-cooperation outcome, 50. Then, in the full cooperation equilibrium,*
 981 *unlike in the γ'' -scenario, implementing a deviating strategy that can change the outcome to partial cooperation*
 982 *size 12 makes the player indifferent between a full cooperation and partial cooperation size 12. That is, while*
 983 *under γ'' a strategy profile in full cooperation equilibrium must be pivoting-proof towards a strategy that leads*
 984 *to partial cooperation with 12 cooperators (3 defectors earning 46), under γ''' it is not the case.*

985 ***Partial cooperation***

986 *Let's turn to partial cooperation equilibria. These equilibria are predicated on the notion of the minimum profitable*
 987 *number of cooperators such that their payoff is at least as large as the status quo payoff from full defection. This*
 988 *size is determined by $g(\gamma) := \lceil n/\gamma \rceil$. Naturally, several sizes of partially cooperative equilibrium outcomes may*
 989 *be possible depending on γ and n . Strategies leading to partial cooperation outcomes with fewer than $g(\gamma)$*

^{†††} Recall that the entries in the vector indicate each player's threshold in terms of the **total** number of players (including themselves) that one requires to cooperate in order for one to cooperate as well.

990 contributors are off-equilibrium. It is easy to see that the unconditional cooperation strategy ($k = 0$) is ruled out
991 consequently.

992 On the other hand, and critically hinging on γ , a given strategy profile —whose structure enables partial
993 cooperation of a certain size— may present a scenario in which a defector is incentivized to switch strategy to
994 increase cooperation and thereby improve her payoff. Hence, when analyzing the structural characteristics of
995 strategy profiles in partial cooperation equilibrium, we must take the above into account. To see this, suppose that
996 we are in a strategy profile, \bar{x} , where the outcome results in \bar{k} players cooperating, such that $g(\gamma) \leq \bar{k} \leq f(\gamma)$.
997 Then the cooperation size necessary for a defecting player to switch strategy and getting a better or equal payoff
998 is given by r , such that $\left\lceil \frac{n}{\gamma} + \bar{k} \right\rceil \leq r \leq n$. Accordingly, for \bar{x} to constitute an equilibrium, we must not only get
999 rid of arrangements of strategies in this profile that allow for cooperation outcomes with fewer than $g(\gamma)$
1000 contributors but also discard those that might lead to cooperation outcomes of size greater than or equal to
1001 $\left\lceil \frac{n}{\gamma} + \bar{k} \right\rceil$ —unless the payoff of a defector in a cooperation outcome of size \bar{k} is exactly equal to the payoff for
1002 a cooperator in an cooperation outcome of size $\left\lceil \frac{n}{\gamma} + \bar{k} \right\rceil$. In which case, the player remains indifferent between
1003 defecting and cooperating.

1004 In a nutshell, a range of partial cooperation sizes may exist. To make further progress, we have identified
1005 conditions that are contingent on γ for a strategy profile to be a partial cooperation equilibrium. First, for a certain
1006 partial cooperation size greater or equal to $g(\gamma)$, a player who ends up cooperating has no incentives to switch
1007 strategy to end up defecting. For certain values of γ , this condition alone is both necessary and sufficient.
1008 However, for other values of γ , it remains necessary but no longer sufficient, as the equilibrium profile will require
1009 a second condition: it is not possible that a player switches strategy that takes her from defection to cooperation
1010 in an outcome where both group cooperation and her individual payoffs increase. In this scenario, the two
1011 conditions together are necessary and sufficient to ensure that no player can profit by unilaterally changing their
1012 strategy to alter the outcome to achieve better payoffs.

1013 *Example 3*

1014 *Consider again the scenarios $n = 15$, $e = 10$ with $\gamma' = 1.8$ and $\gamma'' = 4.5$ from the previous example. Let us see*
1015 *first the case under γ' . Here we have that $f(\gamma') = 7$ and $g(\gamma') = 9$. Then, partial-cooperation outcomes from*
1016 *sizes 1 to 8 are not attractive for a player within a full-defection outcome. The minimum profitable size of partial*
1017 *cooperation that yields higher payoffs in this situation is 9. A player would earn 10.8 by cooperating, whereas in*
1018 *the full defection case, she would earn 10. At the same time, observe that cooperation size from 9 to even 15*
1019 *provides higher incentives for a player to cooperate compared to full defection. We have already checked the case*

for the equilibrium conditions of full cooperation outcome in the previous example. So now let us see the case of partial cooperation outcome equilibrium of sizes from 9 to 14. We must consider the fact that cooperators in those outcomes have incentives to deviate to smaller sizes of cooperation. Let us take the outcome where exactly 9 players cooperate (6 players defect). Under what conditions is this outcome sustained by an equilibrium strategy profile? The answer is that the configuration of strategies is such that switching a strategy leading to an outcome in which the size of the cooperation is any number from 1 to 8 is not possible. A strategy profile that fulfils this condition, for instance, is $(2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,9,11,12,13,14,15,16)^1$. Analogously, the outcome 10 cooperators (5 defectors) will be sustained through an equilibrium when partial cooperation of any size from 2 to 9 cannot occur by deviating. Following this reasoning, we characterize the partial cooperation equilibrium conditions of the rest of cooperation sizes (11 – 14). On the other hand, further constraints are necessary for a strategy profile to be an equilibrium under γ'' . Observe that $g(\gamma'') = 4$. Consider the outcome in which 4 players cooperate and 11 defect, implying that $8 \leq r \leq 15$. Consequently, any strategy profile that leads to this outcome remains an equilibrium as long as the following two conditions are met. First, a deviation from a cooperative player cannot result in an outcome of partial cooperation whose size ranges from 1 to 3. Second, a deviation from a defecting player cannot result in a cooperative outcome whose size ranges from 8 to 15. For example, the profile $(2,3,4,4,6,7,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,16)^1$ is an equilibrium. The conditions for the other partial-cooperation sizes can be determined by applying the above logic.

Example 4

One relevant case arises when $n=2$ and $\gamma' = 1.8$. In this scenario, $g(\gamma') = 2$, indicating that the minimum profitable cooperative outcome size corresponds to full cooperation, which is uniquely determined.

Full defection

Finally, let us outline the full defection outcome equilibrium conditions. First, trivial strategy profile in which everyone uses the unconditional *defection* strategy prevails as an equilibrium case. Next, the equilibrium profile leading to full defection outcome requires that no combination of strategies in a strategy profile triggers the possibility of a cooperative outcome whose size is at least $g(\gamma)$, except when $g(\gamma)=n/\gamma$ (in this case, the partial cooperation outcome size yields the same benefits as full defection outcome). In other words, cooperation sizes of 1, 2, . . . , $g(\gamma)-1$ are not profitable for a player comparing to the full defection status quo. Even further, since we are considering a full defection outcome, it is also clear that the strategy of unconditional cooperation has no room here. The presence of at least two times the unconditional defection strategy is another characteristic of this equilibrium profile for $n \geq 3$.

1050 *Example 5*

1051 *Take the parameter values of example 3. A strategy profile under γ' constitutes a full defection outcome*
1052 *equilibrium if no deviation can cause a cooperative outcome whose size is at least 9. To illustrate, the profile*
1053 *$(2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,16)^1$ provides insight into this condition. Likewise, a strategy profile under γ''*
1054 *defines a full defection outcome equilibrium when cooperative outcome sizes between 4 to 15 are not achievable*
1055 *through unilateral strategy deviations. The profile $(2,3,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,16)^1$ further illustrates this*
1056 *case.*